

Research Article

Study on Overlying Rock Movement and Surface Highway Deformation Under Deep Mining–Induced Fluid–Solid Coupling Effects

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Current research on deep mining–induced overburden movement and highway deformation has neglected the amplification effect of fluid seepage–rock mass deformation coupling interactions on differential settlement, while predominantly focusing on highway alignments parallel or orthogonal to underlying working faces. This study investigates the Hongqinghe Coal Mine in Ordos through FLAC3D numerical simulation and field monitoring, analyzing overburden movement and surface deformation patterns of oblique–parallel highway alignments under deep mining–induced fluid–solid coupling effects. Key findings reveal the following: (1) coal extraction induces stress redistribution in overburden strata, triggering dynamic pore water pressure evolution and seepage path reorganization. Mining-induced fracture connectivity establishes hydraulic connections between deep aquifers and goaf, with peak pore water pressure reaching 2.8 MPa followed by rapid dissipation due to enhanced permeability, exacerbating nonlinear surface subsidence. (2) Vertical stresses in overburden strata undergo abrupt adjustments within the 600–800-m depth range, exhibiting heterogeneous unloading responses that drive highway differential settlement. (3) Spatial relationships between highways and goafs (parallel/oblique) significantly influence deformation characteristics. The parallel alignment shows maximum settlement of 817.91 mm dominated by edge tensile stresses, while oblique sections experience settlement extremum up to 825.64 mm under compound stress fields, primarily exhibiting longitudinal compressive deformation. This research elucidates the response mechanisms governing overburden movement–seepage evolution–surface deformation in deep mining conditions, providing theoretical support for mining-area highway protection and extraction scheme optimization.

Keywords: coal mining beneath highways; deep mining; fluid–solid coupling; numerical simulation; oblique working faces

1. Introduction

As a crucial energy base in China, the deep coal resource exploitation in the Ordos Basin has progressively extended to depths exceeding 1 km [1, 2]. The region features complex geological structures, with massive sandstone–mudstone strata widely distributed. The low permeability and high mechanical strength of these strata significantly influence rock strata movement and surface subsidence during deep mining [3–6]. Within the basin, multilayered groundwater systems—such as Cambrian–Ordovician karst water and

Cretaceous fissure water—dynamically interact with the sandstone–mudstone strata [7–9]. During mining activities, strata movement alters aquifer permeability, triggering pore water pressure redistribution. This process further modifies the stress field of rock masses through fluid–solid coupling effects, ultimately shaping the spatiotemporal evolution of surface subsidence [10–14]. While the high load-bearing capacity of thick sandstone–mudstone strata may delay subsidence progression, their brittle fracture tendencies and uncertainties in hydraulic boundary conditions could exacerbate localized deformation, posing potential threats to

critical transportation infrastructure such as highways and coal transport lines traversing mining areas [15–18]. Consequently, unraveling the dynamic feedback mechanisms between overburden movement and fluid–solid coupling effects during deep mining holds a significant engineering value.

Research on overburden movement and highway deformation mechanisms under the interplay of deep mining and fluid–solid coupling effects has achieved notable progress. Peixian [19] systematically revealed the dynamic evolution of surface movement parameters in deep mining using genetic algorithm–based inversion of probability integral method parameters, providing a theoretical foundation for fluid–solid coupling analysis. Xuchun et al. [20] demonstrated through numerical simulations that the surface subsidence coefficient decreases with increasing mining depth under deep mining conditions, highlighting the limitations of traditional shallow-depth empirical models in deep mining applications. Hu et al. [21] utilized FLAC3D coupling models to uncover the dynamic interaction mechanisms between unconsolidated layers and bedrock in deep mining, revealing spatially heterogeneous horizontal displacements on both sides of goaf areas that critically influence differential settlement of highway subgrades. Liujuan et al. [22] emphasized that existing deep mining prediction models predominantly rely on elastic mechanics theory, neglecting the nonlinear impacts of permeability evolution in rock masses under fluid–solid coupling on surface movement, potentially leading to systematic deviations in highway deformation predictions. Shaokun et al. [23] further incorporated depth-dependent porosity and permeability coefficients, discovering that fluid–solid coupling amplifies surface settlement by 15%–20%. Liyuan et al. [24] employed finite element analysis to elucidate interaction patterns between goaf areas and highways, demonstrating that mining depth, thickness, and multilayer repeated mining significantly affect surface uneven settlement. Guang's [25] FLAC3D simulations revealed that increased working face length destabilizes equilibrium arches in overlying strata, markedly enlarging surface subsidence magnitude and influence ranges, prompting recommendations to control face length for reduced highway deformation risks.

Existing studies exhibit limitations in addressing the interaction mechanisms between overburden movement and surface infrastructure. Research on deep mining–induced overburden movement and highway deformation has yet to fully account for the amplification effects of fluid seepage–rock deformation coupling on differential settlement. For instance, Jie et al. [26] uncovered deformation patterns of oblique-crossing highways in sandstone–mudstone strata but omitted the influence of pore water pressure variations under seepage fields. This study integrates fluid–solid coupling dynamics with overburden movement mechanisms to investigate the impacts of deep mining on highways intersecting both obliquely and parallel to working faces, thereby providing theoretical foundations and technical support for safety assessments and disaster prevention in overlying engineering projects above goaf areas.

2. Model Establishment

2.1. Mining Area and Highway Overview. The Hongqinghe Coal Mine is located in Yijinhuoluo Banner, Inner Mongolia, with an annual designed production capacity of 8 million tons. Its primary mining layer is the 3-1 coal seam. The mining area exhibits stable geological structures, characterized by a gentle undulating terrain with higher elevations in the northeast and lower elevations in the southwest, lacking fold structures or magmatic intrusion activities. Within the mining area, the Wu'a Line (X624) highway obliquely crosses above the 3⁻¹501 working face (Figure 1). This highway features a two-way two-lane Class II asphalt concrete pavement with a designed speed of 80 km/h, a total subgrade height of 1.5 m, and a pavement width of 12 m. Deep coal seam mining may induce geohazards such as differential subgrade settlement, pavement cracking, and linear curvature changes due to mining-induced overburden deformation. As the first working face in the Fifth Mining District, the 3⁻¹501 working face has a strike length of 3500 m, a dip length of 300 m, and an average mining depth of 798 m, utilizing fully mechanized mining technology. The coal seam thickness ranges from 6.1–7.5 m (average 6.75 m), with a dip angle of approximately 1°, indicating deep-seated near-horizontal mining characteristics.

2.2. Parameter Selection. The stratigraphic layers were determined based on the coal seams, roof and floor conditions, and the comprehensive geological columnar chart of the Hongqinghe Coal Mine. Given the complexity of the actual strata, which contain numerous interlayers, appropriate simplifications were applied to the real stratigraphy [27]. The distribution of rock layers and their associated physical–mechanical parameters in the numerical simulation model are listed in Table 1.

Based on field exploration and hydrogeological data, the simulation area is divided into 4 aquifers and 3 aquicludes. Through fluid–solid coupling calculations, this study investigates the movement of overlying strata and deformation patterns of surface highways under the combined effects of deep mining and fluid–solid coupling. The distribution of aquifers/aquicludes and associated fluid parameters in the numerical simulation model are detailed in Table 2.

2.3. Determination of Model Area and Modeling. Based on actual regional conditions, the working face has an average mining thickness of 6.8 m, an average mining depth of 798 m, a strike length of 3500 m, and a dip length of 300 m. The total height of the overlying highway pavement subgrade is 1.5 m, with a total width of 18 m. According to the stratigraphic divisions in Table 1 and the aquifer/aquiclude divisions in Table 2, Rhino software was used for modeling, and the model was imported into FLAC3D for parameter assignment. The model dimensions are 3600 × 900 × 852 m, with a three-dimensional grid constructed along the dip direction (*y*-axis) and strike direction (*x*-axis) to simulate the mining advancement process. The Mohr–Coulomb constitutive model was selected for the rock and soil mass.

FIGURE 1: Relative position of the highway.

TABLE 1: Rock layer distribution and physical–mechanical parameters.

Level number	Lithology	Thickness (m)	Density (kg·m ⁻³)	Elasticity modulus (GPa)	Poisson ratio	Cohesive (MPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Internal friction angle(°)
1	Highway layer	1.50	2100	0.52	0.32	0.21	—	38
2	Quaternary soil layer	8.50	1850	2.30×10^{-2}	0.28	4.80×10^{-3}	—	23
3	Gray-purple mudstone	328.00	2702	5.10	0.29	0.31	0.61	31
4	Silty mudstone	106.00	2640	4.80	0.26	0.38	0.59	29
5	Gray-green mudstone	34.00	2698	4.90	0.31	0.29	0.59	29
6	Sandy mudstone	182.00	2635	6.30	0.24	0.44	0.72	32
7	Conglomerate sandstone	80.25	2685	10.00	0.20	0.62	0.85	38
8	Fine-grained sandstone	53.00	2660	9.10	0.21	0.51	0.77	36
9	Coal seam	6.75	1450	4.70	0.26	0.92	3.60×10^{-2}	44
10	Light-yellow mudstone	6.80	2678	6.00	0.23	0.76	0.81	32
11	Fine-grained sandstone	4.80	2730	9.30	0.22	1.35	0.83	37
12	Siltstone	30.00	2705	8.90	0.20	0.83	0.84	34
13	Sandy mudstone	10.40	2685	5.50	0.25	0.78	0.83	33

Aquifers and aquicludes were assigned isotropic and impermeable properties, respectively. The model contains 413,687 elements and 246,514 nodes. Section A of the model is an outer-edge highway extending parallel to the goaf strike, approximately 800 m in length. Section B crosses obliquely over the goaf, extending approximately 1600 m. Three monitoring lines were arranged along the highway axis: the S1 monitoring line (far from the goaf), the S2 monitoring line (highway center), and the S3 monitoring line (adjacent to the goaf). The positions of the model, highway sections, and monitoring lines are shown in Figure 2.

3. Fluid–Solid Coupling Principles and Boundary Settings

3.1. Principles of Fluid–Solid Coupling. When performing fluid–solid coupling simulations using FLAC3D, the following governing equations and their coupling relationships are primarily involved [28–30]:

The seepage continuity equation is as follows:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(k_{ij} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x_j} \right) + Q = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (n\rho_w), \quad (1)$$

TABLE 2: Distribution of aquifers/aquicludes and fluid parameters.

Level number	Aquifer/aquiclude description	Thickness (m)	Permeability coefficient ($\text{cm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)	Porosity	Fluid density ($\text{g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$)
1	Quaternary (Q) unconsolidated layer phreatic aquifer	5	1.0×10^{-4}	0.5	1000
2	Lower cretaceous Zhidan Group (K1zh) clastic rock Pore-fissure phreatic aquifer	468	1.6×10^{-5}	0.1	1000
3	Jurassic Zhiluo formation sandstone Pore-fissure confined aquifer	262.25	1.8×10^{-8}	0.1	1000
4	Yan'an formation Member 3 aquiclude (roof of no. 3 coal seam)	53	—	—	—
5	Coal seam	6.75	1.0×10^{-4}	0.5	1000
6	Aquiclude at base of no. 3 coal seam	10	—	—	—
7	No. 6 coal Group clastic rock pore-fissure Confined aquifer (top of aquifer)	33.6	1.6×10^{-5}	0.2	1000
8	Aquiclude at top of no. 6 coal seam	8.4	—	—	—

FIGURE 2: Numerical model diagram.

where k_{ij} is the permeability coefficient tensor (m/s), p is the pore water pressure (Pa), Q is the fluid source term, n is the porosity ($\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$), and ρ_w is the fluid density (kg/m^3).

The effective stress principle is as follows:

$$\sigma'_{ij} = \sigma_{ij} - \alpha p \delta_{ij}, \quad (2)$$

where σ'_{ij} is the effective stress tensor (Pa), σ_{ij} is the total stress tensor (Pa), and α is the Biot coefficient.

The modified Darcy's law is as follows:

$$v_i = -k_{ij} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (p + \rho_w g x_i), \quad (3)$$

where v_i is the seepage velocity component (m/s) and g is the gravitational acceleration (m/s^2).

The dynamic coupling equation for permeability coefficient is as follows:

$$k = k_0 * \exp(\beta * \epsilon_v), \quad (4)$$

where k_0 is the initial permeability coefficient (m/s), β is the coupling coefficient, and ϵ_v is the volumetric strain.

3.2. Hydraulic Boundary Settings. Under the fluid–solid coupling effect, the surface subsidence results under constant-head permeable boundary conditions are more accurate compared to impermeable boundaries [31]. Therefore, the hydraulic boundaries are defined as follows:

1. The model's lateral sides are set as permeable boundaries with fixed pore water pressure;
2. The model bottom is set as an impermeable boundary;
3. The model top is set as a permeable boundary.

4. Analysis of Numerical Simulation Results

Parameters were assigned to the model to analyze the pore water pressure field, vertical stress field, overburden-surface vertical displacement, and highway movement and

deformation. The initial geostatic equilibrium displacement nephogram is shown in Figure 3. Figure 3 reflects the displacement field of the model under gravity loading without mining disturbance. Near-zero displacement values around the highway structural layer directly correlate with its high elastic modulus (0.52 GPa) and reinforcement effect (compared to the surrounding Quaternary soil layer modulus of only 0.023 GPa). This displacement suppression phenomenon demonstrates the significant constraining effect of the rigid highway structure on strata deformation. This equilibrium state provides a reliable baseline for subsequent mining disturbance analysis, validating the successful initialization of the model's self-weight stress field. The initial displacement was reset to zero, and the excavation process was simulated in the model.

4.1. Pore-Water Pressure Analysis. Through postprocessing of the numerical simulation results, a profile was cut along the central strike line of the model to obtain the pore-water pressure nephogram within the rock layers, as shown in Figure 4. A vertical monitoring line was established from the surface to the bottom at the center of the working face. The pore-water pressure variation curve derived from continuous monitoring data is presented in Figure 5.

As shown in Figures 4 and 5, coal seam excavation activities significantly alter the vertical distribution pattern of pore-water pressure. Prior to excavation, pore-water pressure exhibits a stable linear increase with depth. Within the depth range of 200 to 737.6 m, the pressure gradually accumulates from an initial value of 0 MPa to a peak of 8.3 MPa. When the seepage path extends to the aquiclude, pore-water pressure gradually dissipates due to hindered drainage. In the deep confined aquifer, pore-water pressure rises again to 6.9 MPa. This regular increase aligns with the characteristics of phreatic aquifers, indicating that the strata are dominated by self-weight stress under natural conditions, with pore-water pressure essentially proportional to depth, reflecting a hydrostatic equilibrium state in undisturbed conditions.

FIGURE 3: Initial in situ stress equilibrium displacement nephogram.

FIGURE 4: Pore-water pressure nephogram. (a) Profile before excavation. (b) Profile after excavation.

FIGURE 5: Pore-water pressure variation curve.

Further analysis reveals that the observed pore-water pressure concentration on both model sides (Figures 4(a) and 4(b)) stems from the combined effect of hydraulic

boundary constraints and stratigraphic heterogeneity. Specifically, lateral boundaries configured as constant-head permeable boundaries (Section 2.2) drive fluid flow toward these low-pressure zones, while the spatial correspondence of these regions with the Jurassic Zhiluo Formation sandstone confined aquifer (Level 3 in Table 2)—characterized by extremely low permeability ($1.8 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$)—restricts vertical fluid migration, leading to pore-water accumulation near the boundaries. Additionally, the abrupt change in the pre-excavation pore pressure curve (Figure 5) is primarily attributed to the barrier effect of Level 4 aquiclude (Yan'an Formation Member 3, coal seam roof). This aquiclude impedes vertical fluid transfer, causing energy accumulation in the overlying confined aquifer (Level 3), whereas free drainage in the underlying coal seam aquifer (Level 5, permeability coefficient $1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$) establishes a steep hydraulic gradient across the aquiclude, manifesting as the observed pressure discontinuity.

After mining completion, the overlying strata undergo bending deformation under vertical stress concentration, causing pore water within the rock mass to displace under compression and accumulate locally in upper regions. Pore-water pressure reaches a peak of 2.8 MPa at 475 m before diminishing. Within the 644–850-m depth interval, driven

by mining-induced fracture development and discontinuous rock layer bending, pore-water seepage channels become fully interconnected, pressure gradients dissipate, and pore-water pressure approaches zero. This demonstrates that coal seam mining profoundly modifies the deep hydrogeological system, revealing the driving role of vertical stress redistribution on groundwater migration and the disruption of original pressure gradients by fracture-dominated seepage pathways. These findings reflect the coupling between rock mass structural damage and seepage field reconstruction under mining disturbances. Fundamentally, discontinuous rock layer deformation caused by mining compromises aquiclude integrity, establishing hydraulic connectivity between deep aquifers and the goaf, leading to systematic instability through rapid groundwater drainage.

4.2. Vertical Stress Analysis. Through postprocessing of the numerical simulation results, a profile was cut along the central strike line of the model to obtain the vertical stress nephogram within the rock layers, as shown in Figure 6. A vertical monitoring line was established from the surface to the bottom at the center of the working face. The vertical stress variation curve derived from continuous monitoring data is presented in Figure 7.

As shown in Figures 6 and 7, vertical stress under gravity exhibits an approximately linear increase with depth before excavation. From the surface to the model bottom, the stress value gradually increases from 0 to -17.7 MPa, consistent with the typical characteristics of self-weight stress in rock strata. After excavation, influenced by rock layer disturbance and fluid–solid coupling effects, the stress field displays a nonlinear distribution. Within the 0–200-m depth range, the stress distribution remains close to the initial state, with the curve shape nearly parallel to the pre-excitation trend, indicating limited unloading effects on shallow surrounding rock. In the 200–600-m depth interval, the surrounding rock stress demonstrates significant nonlinear evolution: During the initial stage (200–412 m), stress increases steadily, reaching a peak of 4.6 MPa at 412 m; subsequently (412–600 m), stress enters a gradual release phase with a decline rate of approximately 0.015 MPa/m; within the 600–800-m interval, the stress field undergoes abrupt adjustments, sharply dropping to 0 MPa, followed by secondary stress concentration, recovering to 1.1 MPa at 850 m. The curve fluctuations reflect the nonuniformity of surrounding rock stress release, directly characterizing the heterogeneous unloading response of deep surrounding rock under excavation disturbance.

Further analysis reveals that this nonlinear stress evolution arises from synergistic interactions between fluid–solid coupling and mining-induced unloading responses within the rock mass (Figure 7). In the unloading-dominated phase (200–600 m), the stress peak observed at 412 m (4.6 MPa) aligns spatially with the conglomerate sandstone layer (Level 7 in Table 1), where the high stiffness (elasticity modulus 10.00 GPa) causes significant stress concentration; the subsequent stress release directly manifests the unloading effect triggered by bending settlement of the

overlying strata. During the fluid–solid coupling transition (600–800 m Zhidan Group), the dramatic stress plunge to near-zero values stems fundamentally from the reorganization of the seepage field driven by mining fracture development: Fracture development within the 644–850-m depth range leads to a permeability surge, causing the rapid collapse of pore water pressure (Figure 5), which in turn triggers a sudden mutation in the effective stress (as governed by the effective stress principle, as shown in equation (2)). The subsequent stress recovery to 1.1 MPa at 850-m depth indicates secondary stress concentration occurring within the underlying floor strata (Levels 10–13 in Table 1).

4.3. Coevolution Law of Overburden-Surface Vertical Displacement. Postprocessing the numerical simulation results yields the surface subsidence nephogram shown in Figure 8. A cross section along the model's strike centerline reveals the internal vertical displacement nephogram of the rock strata in Figure 9. At the center of the working face, a vertical monitoring line was established from the surface to the bottom. The vertical displacement variation curve derived from continuous monitoring data is presented in Figure 10.

As shown in Figures 8 and 9, after mining completion, the area exhibits distinct basin-shaped displacement distribution characteristics. In terms of overall morphology, the model displays a symmetrical pattern with significant vertical displacement in the central region and displacement attenuation at the edges, reflecting a spatial response relationship with the excavation zone. Horizontally, displacement follows a parabolic distribution: minimal at both sides and maximal at the center, with the displacement field symmetric about the geometric midline. The maximum vertical displacement is concentrated in the central area of the goaf, while the minimum displacement occurs at its boundary ends.

Vertically, deformation gradients in the overburden strata above the coal seam vary markedly: The immediate roof rock strata near the goaf exhibit the largest downward bending, forming a “gentle upper, steep lower” deformation gradient as subsidence weakens upward toward the surface. The coal-seam floor uplifts under goaf influence, with the immediate floor showing the most pronounced heave, directly indicating stress redistribution in rock layers induced by mining.

Figure 10 quantifies this vertical deformation heterogeneity through the displacement-depth curve along the central monitoring line. Near the surface zone, the displacement magnitude is minimal. As depth increases, displacement increases sharply; this steep gradient directly validates the “gentle upper, steep lower” deformation pattern described above, indicating that overburden bending is most intense close to the goaf. Below the coal seam, the curve transitions to positive values, indicating uplift occurring in the floor strata. The immediate floor exhibits the most significant uplift, aligning with the floor deformation observed in Figure 9 caused by stress redistribution. This figure highlights how fluid–solid

FIGURE 6: Vertical stress contour plot. (a) Profile before excavation. (b) Profile after excavation.

FIGURE 7: Vertical stress variation curve.

FIGURE 8: Surface subsidence nephogram.

FIGURE 9: Vertical displacement nephogram of rock strata.

FIGURE 10: Vertical displacement variation curve.

coupling amplifies nonlinear subsidence through mechanisms such as stress-driven pore pressure dissipation and heterogeneous unloading.

4.4. Analysis of Highway Movement and Deformation

4.4.1. Highway Settlement Analysis. Highways are linear structures. When the settlement amounts of different sections vary, uneven settlement occurs [26]. To analyze the distribution characteristics of surface settlement during working face mining, Figure 11 illustrates the evolution of highway settlement under different advancing positions via nephograms, while Figure 12 reveals the relationship between the position of the mining working face and the settlement value at the highway's center point.

As shown in the simulation results in Figure 11, the surface deformation zone during mining exhibits a progressive expansion characteristic, with the maximum subsidence area migrating synchronously with the working face advancement direction. Section A, located outside the goaf, experiences weak surface deformation effects, while Section B, which diagonally crosses the goaf, shows significant differential subsidence due to its spatial oblique intersection

with the mining area. This spatial positional difference leads to distinct deformation response characteristics between the two sections.

From Figures 11 and 12, when mining progresses to 1/5, the deformation response of Section A (outside the goaf) is weak, with a subsidence peak of 156.50 mm at mileage 169 m. As mining extends to 2/5, the deformation of this section shows gradient growth, and the subsidence peak shifts to mileage 346 m with a value of 475.74 mm. With further mining advancement to 3/5 and 4/5, the subsidence center continuously migrates forward along the highway axis, reaching peak values of 680.16 and 781.51 mm at mileage 572 and 693 m, respectively. Upon mining completion, Section A stabilizes at a maximum deformation of 817.91 mm as it exits the main deformation influence zone. Concurrently, Section B (obliquely intersecting the goaf) exhibits a subsidence peak of 825.64 mm at mileage 958 m.

4.4.2. Horizontal Deformation Analysis of the Highway.

The longitudinal (x -direction) horizontal displacement nephogram of the surface is shown in Figure 13, the transverse (y -direction) horizontal displacement nephogram of the surface is shown in Figure 14, the longitudinal (x -direction) horizontal displacement curve at the highway center is shown in Figure 15, the transverse (y -direction) horizontal displacement curve of the highway is shown in Figure 16, the longitudinal (x -direction) horizontal deformation curve at the highway center is shown in Figure 17, and the transverse (y -direction) horizontal deformation curve of the highway is shown in Figure 18.

As shown in Figures 13 and 14, after mining completion, the longitudinal horizontal displacement of Section A exhibits a pattern of first increasing and then decreasing along the mining advancement direction. The maximum displacement value of 103.74 mm occurs at mileage 298 m, aligned with the strike direction of the working face. The spatiotemporal evolution of longitudinal horizontal displacement in Section B displays distinct stage characteristics: The initial trend synchronizes with Section A, but within the 1200–2000-m range, displacement fluctuates within ± 10 mm, followed by accelerated decline after 2000 m. The extreme displacement points of this section are located at

FIGURE 11: Highway settlement nephogram during the mining process.

FIGURE 12: Central settlement curve of the highway during the mining process.

FIGURE 13: Horizontal displacement contour plot in the longitudinal (x-direction) of the ground surface.

FIGURE 14: Longitudinal (x -direction) horizontal displacement curve at the highway center.

FIGURE 15: Horizontal displacement contour plot in the transverse (y -direction) of the ground surface.

FIGURE 16: Transverse (y -direction) horizontal curve of the highway.

FIGURE 17: Longitudinal (x -direction) horizontal deformation curve of the highway center.

FIGURE 18: Transverse (y -direction) horizontal deformation curve of the highway.

mileages 813 and 2384 m, with corresponding maximum displacements of 39.76 and -37.64 mm, respectively.

As shown in Figures 15 and 16, after mining completion, the transverse horizontal displacement of Section A stabilizes between -1 and -6.5 mm, with displacement components pointing toward the central axis of the goaf strike line. The fluctuation of S3 is slightly greater than that of S1, with a maximum difference of approximately 2.5 mm. The edge-parallel strike direction may reduce the goaf's impact on the highway. For Section B, transverse horizontal displacement exhibits intense fluctuations with a wave-like pattern: Within 800–1500 m, the displacement direction remains negative. As the highway approaches the goaf center, horizontal displacement increases. After passing the maximum displacement point, the subsidence rate slows and displacement rebound diminishes. Within 1500–2400 m, the

displacement direction shifts to positive, peaks, and then attenuates. S1 shows the largest amplitude, followed by S3, but both trends are highly synchronized, indicating significant overall disturbance from the goaf on the crossing highway section.

As shown in Figure 17, after mining completion, Section A primarily experiences tensile deformation longitudinally due to its alignment with the advancing direction of the coal mining working face. Along the monitoring line from the starting to the ending point, the deformation magnitude shows a decreasing trend, stabilizing in later stages. The maximum tensile deformation occurs at the initial monitoring point of the highway, with a peak value of 0.96 mm/m, consistent with the typical stress release pattern at goaf edges. For Section B, longitudinal horizontal deformation is compression-dominated. Its deformation curve exhibits

central symmetry, displaying a fluctuating pattern throughout without a clear stabilization trend. The maximum horizontal deformation value of -0.15 mm/m occurs at 958 and 2118 m, reflecting the complex stress distribution caused by the section's oblique crossing of the goaf.

As shown in Figure 18, after mining completion, both Section A and Section B are dominated by transverse horizontal tensile deformation but exhibit distinct patterns: Section A, adjacent to the outer edge of the goaf, shows frequent fluctuations influenced by the boundary effect of uneven settlement. A peak of 0.18 mm/m occurs at 500 m, followed by a sharp decline to near-zero values at 800 m, reflecting active stress release in the marginal area but constrained overall deformation by peripheral rock layers. Section B, obliquely traversing the core subsidence zone of the goaf, is significantly affected by continuous collapse. A double-peak pattern emerges in the 1500–2000-m range, reaching a maximum of 0.22 mm/m, followed by rapid decay after 2200 m.

4.4.3. Analysis of Highway Inclination Deformation. The vertical (z -direction) displacement curve at the center of the highway is shown in Figure 19. From Figure 19, the initial settlement at the center of Section A reaches -585 mm, with the overall settlement gradient continuously increasing, peaking at -817.91 mm at mileage 701 m. The settlement curve exhibits a steep unilateral downward trend, reflecting significant boundary effects of the goaf on the marginal area and intense stratigraphic shear deformation. For Section B, the initial settlement at the center is -810 mm, stabilizing after a brief increase and rebounding to 500 mm, reaching a peak settlement of -825.64 mm at mileage 958 m.

The inclination deformation curve at the center of the highway is shown in Figure 20. Due to stratigraphic loss and stress redistribution in the overlying rock layers of the goaf, the surface exhibits funnel-shaped settlement, which induces highway inclination deformation [32]. From Figure 20, the inclination deformation value at the center of Section A first gradually decreases to zero and then increases, with maximum values of -0.43 and 0.069 mm/m, respectively, showing a linear variation with mileage. For Section B, the inclination deformation value at the center shows significant fluctuations throughout, with maximum inclination deformation points at mileages 902 and 2360 m, corresponding to values of -0.15 and 0.34 mm/m, respectively. This indicates that the oblique crossing path amplifies geological disturbances.

5. Comparison Between Field Monitoring and Numerical Simulation Results

To validate the reliability of numerical simulation results, a comparative analysis was conducted using UAV-LiDAR-monitored surface movement data (Figure 21) and numerical simulations during the mining of the $3^{-1}501$ working face in Hongqinghe Coal Mine. This analysis evaluates the accuracy of the fluid–solid coupling model's predictions.

FIGURE 19: Vertical (z -direction) displacement curve at the highway center.

FIGURE 20: Inclination deformation curve at the highway center.

The numerical simulation results indicate that for Section A (parallel to the goaf), the fluid–solid coupling model predicted a maximum subsidence of 817.91 mm, whereas the conventional mechanical model predicted a maximum settlement of 569.65 mm. The measured maximum subsidence along the strike line was 1015 mm. The fluid–solid coupling prediction exceeded the conventional model by 43.6%, highlighting the critical role of seepage effects in settlement generation within this zone. Nevertheless, the fluid–solid coupling prediction remained 19.4% lower than the measured value. This discrepancy is closely linked to the geometric position of Section A at the gob edge. While the model assumed uniform mining rates and homogeneous rock responses, it failed to fully capture the cumulative

FIGURE 21: Surface subsidence map monitored by UAV-LiDAR.

effects of brittle fracture in the actual edge zone of the mining area. Furthermore, the simulation neglected the superimposed disturbance induced by stress release at the gob edge on shallow rock strata. These factors collectively led to conservative subsidence predictions.

For Section B (obliquely crossing the goaf), the fluid–solid coupling model predicted a maximum settlement of 825.64 mm, while the conventional mechanical model predicted 787.10 mm. The measured maximum subsidence along the dip line was 837 mm. The fluid–solid coupling prediction exceeded the conventional model by 4.9%, indicating that while seepage effects exist in obliquely crossing sections, their influence magnitude is less pronounced compared to parallel sections. The minor discrepancy between the model prediction and the dip-line measurement demonstrates that the model effectively captures the primary subsidence trend for obliquely intersecting highway alignments.

6. Conclusions

This paper investigates the impact of fluid–solid coupling effects on overburden movement and surface highway stability during deep mining, revealing the correlation between mining-induced highway deformation patterns and fluid–solid coupling mechanisms. The main conclusions are as follows:

1. Coal seam mining triggers stress redistribution in the overburden, driving dynamic pore water pressure

evolution and seepage path restructuring. Under constant-head permeable boundary conditions, mining-induced fracture development significantly enhances hydraulic connectivity between aquifers and the goaf. Accelerated dissipation of pore water pressure gradients and dynamic permeability changes amplify surface subsidence. Oblique-crossing highways exhibit heightened sensitivity to fluid–solid coupling effects due to spatial geometric disparities relative to the goaf.

2. Discontinuous rock deformation compromises aquiclude integrity, establishing hydraulic connectivity between deep aquifers and the goaf. Pore-water pressure peaks at 2.8 MPa near 475-m depth before rapid dissipation through fracture coalescence. This permeability coefficient evolution intensifies non-linear surface subsidence characteristics.
3. Mining-induced overburden displacement follows a “gentle upper, steep lower” gradient pattern, with immediate roof bending governing basin-shaped surface subsidence. Vertical stress undergoes abrupt adjustments within 600–800-m depth, reflecting heterogeneous unloading responses in deep surrounding rock. Stress release and secondary concentration phenomena exacerbate highway differential settlement.
4. Highway–gob spatial relationships critically govern settlement features: Highways parallel to goaf edges avoid core subsidence zones, experiencing minimal

impacts. Oblique-crossing highways intersecting composite stress fields (mining boundary + highway axis) suffer intensified differential settlement. Under near-horizontal seam mining, maximum subsidence (~825 mm) typically occurs directly above the goaf center.

- Highways parallel to goaf strike align with tensile-dominated zones in surface movement basins. Lateral tensile stresses from overburden caving induce bidirectional subgrade stretching. For oblique-crossing highways, longitudinal deformation exhibits compression dominance under asymmetric stress fields. Transverse deformation remains tensile-dominated, creating combined tension-compression patterns. Accordingly, oblique sections require enhanced longitudinal compressive resistance. Parallel alignments should optimize tensile strength reinforcement at highway edges.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are included within the manuscript and can be used to reproduce the results presented herein through simulation in the FLAC3D software environment.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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